

1 Development and validation of a precise and accurate method to
2 determine polyamine levels in cultured cells.

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24

25 Abstract

26 We describe a robust, fast and accurate method for the quantification of intra-cellular
27 concentrations of the polyamines, putrescine, spermidine and spermine in cultured cells.
28 Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography in combination with Time-of-Flight mass
29 spectrometry was used to obtain high resolution data for the analytes. Assay performance was
30 determined with respect to chromatographic resolution, quantification, analyte recovery and
31 matrix effects. Furthermore, assay variability was determined in a biological context. Based on
32 these variability measurements, minimal detectable effects (MDEs) which would lead to
33 significant differences in a null-hypothesis significance test, were calculated. As such, changes
34 in spermine could be determined with the highest sensitivity with point estimates for the MDEs
35 of 32% between-days and 10% within-days. For spermidine, these values were 38% between-
36 days and 16% within-days. Finally, effects for putrescine were measured least sensitive with
37 43% between-days and 36% within-days. Finally, we employed the method to analyze the
38 impact of polyamine synthesis pathway inhibition and cell culture conditions which are
39 relevant aspects for the interpretation of the biological role of polyamines.

40

41 Introduction

42 Polyamines (PAs) are biologically important metabolites. Due to their primary amino groups,
43 they exist as cations under normal pH. They associate electrostatically with negatively charged
44 macro-molecules like DNA and RNA. As such they play an important role in epigenetic
45 processes. Furthermore, they are involved in redox balance and are associated with neuronal
46 potassium channel activity. Overall, PAs are implicated in different diseases, such as cancer,
47 immune response and neurological disorders [1].

48 There are three different biogenic PA species, namely putrescine (Put), spermidine (Spd) and
49 spermine (Spm). Depending on the cell type, Put, Spd and Spm can have high intracellular
50 concentrations (millimolar levels) and have well-established biological functions. Furthermore,
51 polyamines can be acetylated to form various N-acetylated species. This process is considered
52 a rate limiting step in polyamine metabolism [2]. We have focused this assay exclusively on
53 Put, Spd and Spd.

54 Many methods are available for measuring biological PA concentrations. Most of these
55 methods use some type of chromatography to separate the different PAs before detection with
56 mass spectrometry [3]. Due to the highly polar nature of PAs, many such methods use
57 derivatization [4] or ion-pairing chromatography [5] to increase retention on conventional C18
58 column-chemistries. Derivatization also enables detection by UV or fluorescence.
59 Furthermore, depending on the biological matrix, various types of homogenization and
60 extractions have been described [3; 4; 6]. Some reported methods are very sensitive with a high
61 dynamic range, generally depending on the type of mass spectrometer. Other assays focus on
62 additional analytes, making them more versatile but less optimized for PAs [5]. More
63 cumbersome are methods using derivatization reactions, which introduces more processing
64 steps, and hence, more sources of variation. All these methods have their benefits and

65 drawbacks and although many of these methods have good performance, we decided to
66 establish our own to refine some of their limitations. Some methods described had long run
67 times [7] or lacked proper separation. Moreover, some methods, like ion-pairing
68 chromatography or online SPE, were incompatible with our instrumentation. In any case, none
69 of the available methods used the same equipment available in our lab or were not optimized
70 for the desired biological matrix. Hence, the development of this assay to measure intracellular
71 PA concentrations with ultra-performance liquid chromatography coupled Time-of-Flight mass
72 spectrometry (UPLC-ToF-MS).

73 Chromatography was optimized with respect to carry-over and chromatographic resolution.
74 Furthermore, we have determined dynamic range and lowest limit of quantification (LLOQ) in
75 solution. All other development steps were carried out in a biological context, meaning that we
76 used biological matrix in the various optimization experiments. Extraction and injection liquids
77 were optimized with respect to carry-over, signal intensity and recovery. Furthermore, we
78 describe a method for the determination of ion-suppression due to matrix effects using spiked
79 quality control samples. By using cell extracts to determine inter-, intra-day and measurement
80 variability, it was possible to calculate minimal detectable effects (MDEs) in a realistic,
81 biological scenario using Bayesian estimates.

82 We established a simple, fast, sensitive and well-defined analytical method to measure
83 intracellular concentrations of Put, Spd and Spm in cultured cells. A simple biphasic extraction
84 procedure was used to clean up samples and to extract and concentrate analytes. High-
85 resolution hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC) coupled to ToF-MS was
86 used for chemical analysis.

87 We used our newly established method to determine the effect of inhibition of the enzyme S-
88 adenosylmethionine decarboxylase (SAMDC) by SAM486A on PA pools using $^{13}\text{C}_5$ -

89 methionine as a precursor to track ^{13}C labelled carbons. Since SAM486A is a well-known
90 inhibitor and its effects are well documented, this experiment served as a positive control of
91 the performance of the analytical method. Finally, we used the method to measure intracellular
92 analyte concentrations for DU145 cells that were incubated with different culture media
93 conditions.

94 Methods

95

96 Materials

97 Optima® LC/MS grade water (water), methanol (MeOH), acetonitrile (ACN) and formic acid
98 (FA) were purchased from Fischer Scientific (Loughborough, UK). Ammonium formate
99 (AmFo) and acetic acid (AA) were purchased from Honeywell/Fluka (Seelze, Germany).
100 Chloroform as well as putrescine dihydrochloride, spermidine trihydrochloride and spermine
101 tetrahydrochloride were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). L-Methionine-
102 ¹³C₅ was purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories. SAM486A was kindly provided by
103 Novartis (referenced in [8]). Safe-Lock™ 1.5 mL microtubes were purchased from Eppendorf
104 (Hamburg, Germany). Polypropylene Acquity UPLC 700 µL round 96-well-plates were
105 purchased from Waters (Manchester, UK) as well as silicon/PTFE treated pre-slit seals.

106

107 Solutions

108 Optimized extraction liquid (EL) consisted of 10 mM AA in 50% (v/v) MeOH/water.
109 Optimized resuspension liquid (RL) consisted of 39.8% water, 60% ACN and 0.2% FA (v/v/v).

110

111 Reagents for cell cultures

112 Human prostate carcinoma cell line DU145 (ACC261) was used and purchased from Leibniz-
113 Institut DSMZ (Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen GmbH), which
114 provided authentication certificate, and were tested for mycoplasma every two weeks. Cells

115 were cultured in Dulbecco's modified eagle medium (DMEM, Gibco[™]41966-029 and
116 Penicillin/ Streptomycin (Gibco[™]15140-122) (0.1%) with 10% of Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS)
117 (Gibco[™] 10270-106) or Dialyzed FBS (Thermo Fisher Scientific A3382001). Human Plasma
118 Like-Medium (Thermo Scientific A4899101) was also used as a third approach.

119

120 Cellular assay

121 For the assay variability test, DU145 cells were seeded in four 6-well plates. For each
122 measurement day a single plate was used. To test culture medium conditions, DU145 cells were
123 seeded in 6-well plates in four independent experiments and with 3 technical replicates per
124 experiment. After 6 hours, the cells were attached, and we changed the media to culture them
125 in the three different media (DMEM complete; DMEM dialyzed serum; HPLM) for 48h when
126 they reached a confluence of 80% in the well. Finally, cells were washed three times with
127 abundant phosphate buffered saline (PBS, Gibco[™]14190-034) and snap frozen in liquid
128 nitrogen before they were stored at -80 °C. For inhibition experiments SAM486A was added
129 to DMEM complete medium in a concentration of 500 nM. Moreover, to label Spm and Spd,
130 uniformly ¹³C-labelled methionine (¹³C₅-methionine) was added to DMEM complete medium
131 to obtain a final concentration of 0.2 mM labelled methionine and a total methionine
132 concentration (labelled and unlabelled) of 0.4 mM. For inhibition experiments after 42h,
133 medium was changed to the medium containing SAM486A and ¹³C₅-methionine and cells were
134 further incubated for 6 hours.

135

136

137

138 Optimization of cell extractions

139 To optimize the extraction procedure, two monophasic and one biphasic extraction method
140 were tested. For the monophasic extractions the extraction liquid contained either 50% (M50)
141 or 80% MeOH (M80) in water (v/v). Both solvent mixtures contained 10 mM AA. The
142 extraction liquid of the biphasic method (BP) contained 10 mM AA in 50% MeOH in water
143 (v/v) for the aqueous phase and chloroform for the organic phase.

144 Cells were extracted by putting the six-well culture plates on ice, adding 500 μ L ice-cold
145 extraction liquid to the wells and letting these rest for 15 minutes. Subsequently, the cells were
146 scraped of the bottom of the wells and 400 μ L of this suspension was transferred to 1.5 mL
147 microtubes. For the biphasic extraction 400 μ L chloroform was added to this homogenate.

148 The extractions were agitated for 30 minutes at 1400 rpm and 4 °C and the microtubes were
149 centrifuged for 30 minutes at 14000 rpm (~13200 g) and 4 °C. Next, 250 μ L of the supernatant
150 was transferred to a clean microtube and evaporated to dryness. For the biphasic extraction 250
151 μ L of the aqueous layer was used (top layer). Pellets were resuspended in 150 μ L 60%
152 ACN/40% water (v/v) and measured.

153

154 Analyte recovery

155 Recovery was determined by using samples that were either spiked before (pre-spike) or after
156 extraction (post-spike) and non-spike samples. Extractions were carried out with the biphasic
157 extraction method. For pre-spiked samples, either 100 nM or 1 μ M of the three analytes were
158 spiked in EL which was then used to extract cells. For post-spike samples, analytes were spiked
159 in RL at the same concentrations. Non-spiked samples were worked up without spiking

160 analytes in either liquid. Volumes taken from the aqueous phase for evaporation and for
161 resuspension of the resulting pellets were both 200 μL .

162

163 Sample preparation

164 For variability tests and method application, the biphasic extraction method was used with a
165 slight modification in the transferred volumes. After centrifugation, from each extraction 280
166 μL of the aqueous phase was transferred to a clean 1.5 mL microtube and from this tube 30 μL
167 was transferred to a second 1.5 mL microtube. Thus, each cell extraction results in two
168 microtubes containing 250 μL which content was used for the analytic sample and 30 μL
169 aqueous phase which was used for quality controls (QCs).

170 The aqueous phases were evaporated in a speed vac to dryness in two batches. The 250 μL
171 samples took about 3 hours to fully evaporate and 30 μL samples took about 30 minutes. The
172 pellet of each analytic sample was resuspended in 150 μL RL. The pellets of the QC samples
173 were resuspended sequentially in a single volume which depended on the number of
174 extractions. For each extraction, 9 μL RL was added, *e.g.* when 30 extractions were analyzed,
175 a single volume of $30 \times 9 \mu\text{L} = 270 \mu\text{L}$ was used to resuspend all QC samples. This was done
176 by adding the single volume to an evaporated QC sample, resuspending the pellet and
177 transferring it to the next QC sample *etc.* until all QC samples were resuspended in the single
178 volume.

179 The QC sample was then split into two equal parts. To one part, an equal volume of EL was
180 added. These were used for initialization QCs (QC_{init}) and normal QC samples (QC_0). To the
181 second part, the same volume of 10 μM analyte-spiked EL was added (QC_{spike}). Following the
182 above example, with 30 extractions, two aliquots of 135 μL were created. To one of these,
183 135 μL EL was added and to the other 135 μL 10 μM spiked EL was added. This to ensure that

184 the matrix in the QCs was the same as in the average analytical sample. The QC_{spike}, which had
185 added analyte concentrations of 5 μM , could be used to estimate the matrix effects affecting
186 signal strength.

187 After resuspension, all samples were centrifuged again for 15 minutes at 14000 rpm ($\sim 13200\text{ g}$)
188 and 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Finally, 130 μL of the analytical sample and the total volumes minus 20 μL of the
189 QC samples were transferred to a 96-wells plate for injection on the LCMS system.

190

191 Analytical standards and calibration samples

192 Separate analytical standards of Put, Spd and Spm with a concentration of 100 mM were made
193 in water and stored in 4 mL glass tubes at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for further use. These standards were used to
194 make a pooled solution of 1 mM in water which was stored in a microtube at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for further
195 use. This pooled solution was then used for making calibration curves and QC_{spike} solutions.

196 To make the calibration curve, 100 μL pooled 1 mM analyte solution was added to 300 μL
197 water containing 0.66% (v/v) FA and subsequently 600 μL ACN was added. This resulted in a
198 100 μM solution in RL. This 100 μM solution was diluted ten times in RL to obtain 2 mL 10
199 μM analyte solution. This solution was used to spike the QC_{spike} sample and for the highest
200 point of the calibration curve.

201 The dilution series for the curve was as follows: 10 μM was diluted two times in RL to 5 μM .
202 The 5 μM solution was diluted another two times to 2.5 μM . The 10 μM , 5 μM and 2.5 μM
203 solutions were ten times diluted to obtain 1 μM , 0.5 μM and 0.25 μM . The resulting solutions
204 were again ten times diluted to 0.1 μM , 0.05 μM and 0.025 μM . The 0.025 μM solution was
205 diluted two times, four times to get the following concentration range: 12.5 nM, 6.3 nM, 3.1
206 nM and 1.6 nM. Thus, the curve contained 14 points including a RL blank.

207 Sample sequence

208 The injection sequence used for the variability tests and method application started with the
209 14-point calibration curve, followed by four QC_{init} samples to equilibrate the column. Next a
210 QC₀ and a QC_{spike} were injected followed by the analytical samples. QC₀ and QC_{spike} were
211 injected at regular intervals between the samples and at the end of the sample sequence. The
212 QC interval depended on the number samples and was around 6 to 8 samples. After the final
213 QC set, another calibration curve was injected. The analytical samples were injected in
214 duplicate or in triplicate and in a randomized order.

215

216 Liquid chromatography

217 An Acquity I-Class Plus UPLC system (Waters) was used for chromatographic separations.
218 The system was equipped with a binary solvent manager, a two-position sample manager, a
219 ten-position sample organizer and a column heater. A 12.5'' HPS column active preheater was
220 used to connect the injection valve with the column inlet.

221 LC optimization was carried out by testing different mobile phases and gradients as described
222 in Table 1) and Table 2). The optimized mobile phases consisted of aqueous phase (A)
223 containing water, 0.25% FA (v/v) and 2.5 mM AmFo and an organic phase (B) containing
224 9.75% water, 0.25% FA, 90% ACN (v/v/v) and 2.5 mM AmFo. To prepare the B phase, FA and
225 AmFo were first mixed with water and then ACN was added.

226 Separation was carried out on an Atlantis™ Premier BEH Z-HILIC 1.7 μm 2.1×100 mm
227 column. The column was thermostated at 40 °C. The linear gradient was as follows: 52%A to
228 100%A in 3.5 minutes, constant at 100%A for 0.9 minutes, back to 52%A in 0.1 minutes and
229 constant at 52%A for 1 minute for column equilibration. The flow rate was set to 400 μL/min.

230 Mass spectrometry

231 Mass spectrometric analysis was performed on a SYNAPT G2S instrument (Waters). The
232 instrument was used in full-scan (50-1200 Da) positive electrospray ionization mode. The
233 optimized source settings were as follows: the capillary voltage was set to 200 V, sampling
234 cone voltage to 25 V, source offset voltage to 80 V. Source temperature was 120 °C and
235 desolvation temperature was 450 °C. The cone gas flow was 5 L/h, nebulizer gas flow was 6
236 bar and desolvation gas flow was 600 L/h. All gas flows were nitrogen. Scan rate was set to
237 0.2 seconds. Accurate mass was assured by infusing a lock-mass (Leu-Enk, 100 ppb in 49.9%
238 water, 50% ACN, 0.1%FA (v/v/v), $m/z = 556.2771$) at 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{minute}$ every 60 seconds for 0.5
239 seconds.

240

241 Data analysis

242 Extracted ion chromatograms (EICs) for the protonated forms of the analytes, Put ($m/z =$
243 89.1079), Spd ($m/z = 146.1657$), $^{13}\text{C}_3\text{-Spd}$ ($m/z = 149.1758$), Spm ($m/z = 203.2236$), $^{13}\text{C}_3\text{-Spm}$
244 ($m/z = 206.2336$) and $^{13}\text{C}_6\text{-Spm}$ ($m/z = 209.2437$) were extracted in a 20 mDa window and
245 integrated with TargetLynx software (Waters). EICs were smoothed by taking a two-point
246 average for two iterations. Peak areas were used for further analysis. To determine the fraction
247 of ^{13}C -labelled PAs, the fraction of natural occurring ^{13}C was subtracted from the signal in the
248 mass channels of the $^{13}\text{C}_3$ (Spd/Spm) and $^{13}\text{C}_6$ (Spm) species. All calculations in this manuscript
249 were performed in R (version 4.4.1).

250 Signal data was pretreated to adjust for biases during sample work-up and analysis. Analysis
251 scripts are available (Supplemental information). First, analyte signals were adjusted with
252 median fold-change (MFC) normalization [9; 10]. In short, 1) LCMS features (*i.e.* retention

253 time- m/z pairs) were collected for each sample, including QCs. 2) A reference sample was
254 determined based on the highest number of features. 3) For each sample, each feature was
255 scaled on the value of the reference sample, obtaining fold-change value for each feature over
256 all included samples. 4) The median of the fold-change values for each sample was calculated
257 to obtain the MFC normalization factor for each sample. 5) Analyte signals were divided by
258 the MFC factor. This method adjusts for factors like differences in biological material or
259 variation in extraction between samples and altering detector response during the run.

260 The remaining variation in analyte signals was determined and possibly corrected with QC₀
261 values. 1) The QC₀ signals per analyte were normalized on the first QC₀. 2) For each analyte,
262 a polynomial of the first degree was fitted through the normalized signals by using the injection
263 number as the independent variable. 3) The sample signals were corrected by dividing the
264 signal by the value returned by the polynomial, based on the injection numbers of the samples.
265 If either MFC-normalization or QC-correction did not lead to a median drop in variation
266 between replicate injections, the correction was not used and instead the raw or single-corrected
267 signals were used for further calculations.

268 Qualification was done by using the following algorithm. 1) The median signal in the sample
269 space was determined. 2) The curve concentration with the closest signal to this median signal
270 was chosen as focus concentration. 3) All 4-point log-transformed linear models containing
271 this focus concentration were made, using both curves. 4) Deviation from the nominal curve
272 concentrations were determined for each model. 5) The model for which the least calculated
273 concentrations deviated more than 15% from their nominal values was chosen for sample
274 quantification.

275 To show signal behavior over the entire calibration curve, curves were fitted with log-
276 transformed linear regression to account for the non-linear response of the detector. First,

277 calibration points were excluded that were lower than 12 times the baseline noise (lowest limit
278 of quantification, LLOQ). For the remaining points the concentration (x) and signal (y) values
279 were log transformed. Next, a linear model was fitted to the transformed data. This model can
280 be interpreted as follows: the intercept (α) and slope (β) of the linear model can be used on the
281 non-transformed data as a power-law relationship $y = e^\alpha x^\beta$. To determine a concentration from
282 a signal, the following relation can be used: $x = (y/e^\alpha)^{1/\beta}$. Both curves were used to create the
283 linear model.

284 After obtaining accurate (adjusted) signal and concentration data, various assay metrics were
285 determined. These metrics included extraction efficiency, recovery, signal attenuation due to
286 matrix effects and assay variability from biological and instrumental sources. The final method
287 was used to determine cell concentrations of the analyte for different culture media types. For
288 statistical analysis we used Bayesian multilevel models. Bayesian models combine prior
289 information and the likelihood of the data to generate a posterior distribution of the model
290 parameters. The parameter estimates can then be used to generate posterior distributions of the
291 desired metrics. These models provide the flexibility needed to handle complex data and return
292 full probability distributions for parameters, offering a natural way to quantify uncertainty.

293 All models were given a normal likelihood, truncated at 0, to assure that the posterior samples
294 were strictly positive as is the case for signal or concentration data. Priors for fixed and random
295 effects were normal distributions and priors for standard deviations were exponential
296 distributions. Random effects were assigned where possible for repeated measures, like sample
297 replicates. Experimental groups were treated as fixed effects. Furthermore, the model used to
298 calculate recoveries assured that estimated means for the no-spiked group should always be
299 smaller than that of the pre-spiked group and that of the pre-spiked group should be smaller
300 than that of the post-spiked group, *i.e.* $\mu_0 < \mu_{\text{pre}} < \mu_{\text{post}}$. Bayesian models were written in the
301 probabilistic programming language Stan (version 2.32.2). Posterior parameter estimates for

302 treatment groups, obtained from the various models, were used for further calculations. The
303 code for the various models is available in the Supplementary Information.

304 Extraction efficiency was estimated simply by comparing the group estimates for the different
305 extraction groups. The same was done to estimate cell concentrations for different culture
306 media types. Recovery was determined by first estimating the expected signal ($E[Signal]$) for
307 the pre-spiked, post-spiked, and non-spiked sample groups. Next, baseline-adjusted estimates
308 were obtained by subtracting the expected signal of the non-spiked group from both the pre-
309 spiked and post-spiked estimates. Recovery was then calculated as the ratio of the baseline-
310 adjusted pre-spiked estimate to the baseline-adjusted post-spiked estimate. Mathematically,
311 this is defined as: $R = (E[Signal_{pre}] - E[Signal_0]) / (E[Signal_{post}] - E[Signal_0])$, where
312 $E[Signal_{pre}]$, $E[Signal_{post}]$, and $E[Signal_0]$ represent the expected signal for the pre-spiked,
313 post-spiked, and non-spiked groups, respectively. Attenuation due to matrix effects was
314 determined similarly. By dividing the posterior means of the QC_0 -subtracted QC_{spike} group
315 (spike level at 5 μ M) by the posterior mean of the 5 μ M signal from the calibration curves in
316 solution, attenuation was determined. The calculation was as follows: $A = (Signal_{QC_{spike}} -$
317 $Signal_{QC_0}) / Signal_{curve}$. To determine inter-day, intra-day and measurement variation, the
318 estimates of the relative standard deviations (equivalent to coefficients of variations, %CV) for
319 run, sample and likelihood were used. The relative standard deviations were used to calculate
320 minimal detectable effect (MDE) per analyte. The standard error was calculated using the
321 square root of the sum of variances, assuming $n=6$. The MDE was then determined by
322 multiplying the standard error with the critical t-value for $\alpha=0$ (two-sided, $n=6$).

323 Results and Discussion

324 The method was optimized for chromatography and extraction efficiency until acceptable
325 performance was achieved taking in account chromatographic resolution, signal intensity and
326 carry-over. We tested five mobile phases, seven LC gradients and three extraction methods.
327 Importantly the assay was validated in a biological context. This means that recovery, matrix
328 effects and variability were all determined in the target matrix rather than in BSA solutions or
329 solvent as is the case in some assay validations, for example [6; 7]. This gives a more realistic
330 idea of the assay performance. Finally, we applied the method to determine differences in PA
331 levels for cell cultures, using different culture media conditions.

332

333 LC method optimization

334 Polyamines (PAs) are extremely hydrophilic with logP-values for Put, Spd and Spm of
335 respectively -0.466, -0.504 and -0.543. Therefore, we tested two hydrophilic column
336 chemistries namely BEH AMIDE and BEH Z-HILIC before settling on the latter one. Although
337 the AMIDE column did retain and separated the PAs sufficiently well, the gradients and mobile
338 phases were more complex, and the peak shapes were worse compared to the Z-HILIC column
339 (results not shown).

340 For optimization of the Z-HILIC method we started with optimizing the mobile phase. For
341 this we increased FA and AmFo content in both aqueous and organic phases. This resulted in
342 increased resolution and intensity (Fig. 1). Specifically, higher AmFo content resulted in
343 increased resolution and sharper peaks (*i.e.* MP2 vs. MP3) while increased FA content resulted
344 in increased signal strength (*i.e.* MP3 vs. MP4) (Fig. 1). The highest chromatographic
345 resolutions (Table 3) were obtained with MP5 which contained the highest amount of AmFo.

346 The increase of FA from 0.1% (MP3) to 0.25% (MP4) resulted in approximately 2-times (Put),
347 3-times (Spd) and 10-times (Spm) increase of signal strength. Increase to 0.5% FA (MP5)
348 resulted in only slightly increased (Put) or decreased (Spm) signal strength.

349 Although MP5 gave the best resolution we decided to use MP4 for further optimization. This
350 choice was made to avoid the risk of crystallization of AmFo due to its high concentration
351 (5 mM) in the organic phase. Moreover, higher AmFo concentrations could lead to faster
352 contamination of the ion source and lower column-life. On the other hand, the difference in
353 signal strength and resolution were not critically worse than with MP4.

354 After choosing a mobile phase, the gradient was optimized. For this we varied the initial mobile
355 phase proportions and the gradient time. All gradients showed excellent resolutions (Table 3)
356 with Grad4 and Grad7 as optimal. However, we found that gradients starting below 50% A had
357 some carry-over (not shown) while gradients starting at 50% A or higher showed clean blank
358 injections after injection of a high (10 μ M) analyte concentration. Moreover, increasing
359 gradient time from 2 to 3 minutes increased resolution even further. Therefore, for subsequent
360 analysis we used Grad7, which starts at 52% A and has a gradient time of 3 minutes.

361 Another source of carry-over was the absence of FA in the injection liquid. Signals in blank
362 injections after injection of a 10 μ M PA mix sample without FA showed signals for Spd and
363 Spm, equivalent to nM levels (Fig. 3). These signals disappeared with FA concentrations of
364 0.1% or higher in the injection liquid. Therefore, the injection liquid should at least contain
365 0.1% FA. However, when preparing and measuring samples over various days, we found that
366 0.1% FA injection liquid was not stable during prolonged storage (> 3 days), since carry-over
367 increased over time. This is probably due to the evaporation of FA. Therefore, we increased FA
368 content to 0.2% which resulted in an injection liquid that was stable for at least a week.

369 Injection liquid containing 39.8% water, 60% ACN and 0.2% FA (v/v/v) was used for further
370 experiments.

371

372 Extraction efficiency

373 To optimize the extraction of the targeted analytes from cells, we tested three extraction
374 methods. Given that the volumes subjected to evaporation and subsequent resuspension were
375 the same for each method, the method resulting in the highest signals would be optimal. We
376 found that the M80 method performed worse for all three analytes (Fig. 4A). This might be due
377 to the highly polar nature of the analytes which could cause the analytes to stick to matrix
378 components rather than to dissolve in a high concentration of methanol. The M50 method
379 showed similar performance for Put and Spd but was significantly worse for Spm. This might
380 be due to the same reason as given for M80. However, since Put and Spd are less polar than
381 Spm, the partition equilibrium of Put and Spd over matrix components and solvent may lay
382 more towards solvent in M50 than that of Spd. It could be argued that lowering the MeOH
383 content even further would result in a higher extraction efficiency. However, from experience
384 we found that MeOH content lower than 50% resulted in worse protein precipitation which led
385 to problems such as clogging of the chromatographic column.

386 The best performing extraction for all analytes was the biphasic one (BP). This could be
387 because part of the MeOH dissolves in the chloroform which leaves the aqueous phase more
388 polar and thus dissolves the polyamines better. Moreover, many apolar components were
389 transferred to the organic phase, leaving the sample cleaner.

390

391

392 Analyte recovery

393 After optimizing the extraction liquid, the amount of recovered analyte was determined for two
394 spike levels, *i.e.* 100 nM and 1 μ M. Therefore, cell homogenates were spiked before and after
395 extraction at two levels. Non-spiked samples were then used to subtract background analyte
396 signals. We found good recovery for 1 μ M spike levels (Fig. 4B, Table 4). Recovery for Put
397 was 97% (95%-99%), for Spd 92% (88%-96%) and for Spm 89% (85%-94%). The recovery
398 for 100 nM could not be determined accurately because of the high endogenous signal, relative
399 to the spiked-in concentrations. Although model estimates suggest that recoveries for 100 nM
400 spikes are somewhat lower. However, since the endogenous concentrations were close to the
401 1 μ M spikes, the recovery at 1 μ M should be indicative for regular cell extractions.

402

403 Quantification

404 To illustrate signal behavior as function of nominal curve concentrations, calibration curves
405 were analyzed over the total concentration range. Note that final quantification was done with
406 a legacy method that only uses the part of the curves that are most representative for sample
407 signals. It was found that by using our legacy quantification method, the inter-day assay
408 variability was significantly lower (results not shown).

409 Because older ToF instruments show strong non-linear behavior over extended concentration
410 ranges, curve fitting is not straight forward. Even when a double log-transform was done, there
411 still was some non-linear behavior left. The parts before and after 0.5 μ M have different slopes
412 (Fig. 5A). Therefore, two curves could be fitted for the lower and upper part with a common
413 point at 0.5 μ M. Considering adjusted R^2 values, which did all exceed 0.98, all fits were good.
414 Mean deviations from nominal values for all three analytes, as measured over 5 runs, were all
415 within $\pm 15\%$. This indicates that the assay has high accuracy [11]. The standard error of the

416 mean-intervals (SEM) for Spd and Spm also mostly did not surpass this threshold, the Put SEM
417 -intervals are in most cases somewhat higher indicating that the assay is less accurate for this
418 metabolite. This is not surprising given that the signal-to-noise ratios for Put were relatively
419 low, compared to Spd and Spm.

420 For 2 μ L injections, the LLOQs for Put and Spd were around 10 nM while that of Spm was
421 around 3 nM. Since curve samples were measured in solution no background signals had to be
422 extracted which increased the sensitivity of the assay. However, a disadvantage of measuring
423 calibration samples in the absence of matrix is that ion-suppression in the biological samples
424 is not accounted for. However, by using spiked and non-spiked QC samples an estimation of
425 matrix effects could be made as explained in the next section. The sample concentrations could
426 then be adjusted accordingly.

427 In any case, the LLOQ levels were more than sufficient to determine concentrations for the
428 number of cells that were used for variability tests, *i.e.* 500k cells per sample. For these
429 samples, vial concentrations for the analytes, *i.e.* 650 nM for Put, 1.8 μ M for Spd and 250 nM
430 for Spm, lay well above their LLOQs.

431

432 Signal attenuation

433 Matrix components can cause analyte signals to change in intensity with respect to signals
434 measured in pure solvent solutions. Normally, matrix effects lead to a decrease in ionization
435 efficiency and hence a decrease in signal strength. This could be a problem when a calibration
436 curve is prepared in solution as in this study. In the case of signal attenuation in matrix, this
437 could lead to lower apparent concentrations.

438 There are various ways to correct for these effects. Obviously, a curve could be prepared in
439 matrix. However, as explained, this would lead to an increase in the quantification limit due to
440 the high endogenous background. Another way to correct is to add an internal standard to the
441 resuspension liquid. This internal standard could be a non-endogenous compound with similar
442 chemical properties or a stable isotope-labelled analyte. Both these methods have drawbacks.
443 We added cadaverine (Cad), a chemically similar, non-endogenous compound, as an internal
444 standard. However, this surprisingly led to severe suppression of the Put signal. This was
445 presumably associated with the fact that Cad and Put coeluted and that the concentration of the
446 spiked Cad (10 μ M) was high. Moreover, as we will see later, adding a biosimilar compound
447 will not be sufficient to correct for all analyte attenuations. As for stable-labelled analytes, at
448 the time of development, besides being very expensive these compounds were only available
449 in small quantities, which made it very challenging to make accurate stock solutions.
450 Additionally, if metabolic flux experiments are carried out using stable isotope tracers, these
451 internal standards could interfere with labelled analyte signals.

452 Therefore, we chose to correct for signal attenuation by injecting a spiked QC sample after
453 each normal QC. Then, the difference in signal between these two samples was compared to a
454 sample of the same analyte concentration but in solution. We found that attenuations varied
455 strongly between analytes. The signal of Put in matrix was 0.35-times the signal in solution,
456 for Spd it was 0.59-times and for Spm 0.87-times (Table 4). This also shows that a single
457 internal standard is not enough to correct for the various attenuation effects.

458 However, the measured concentrations in this study were not corrected for these effects because
459 unfortunately we did not include this method in some of the validation runs. Therefore, if this
460 method was applied to only some of the runs, a comparison over all runs (necessary to estimate
461 assay variability) would not be possible. Notwithstanding, the authors do recommend that this
462 correction should be made when the method is applied in future studies.

463 Assay variability

464 We determined sources of variation by measuring analyte concentrations in cell cultures over
465 four days (Fig. 6). This validation process differs somewhat from a conventional biological
466 assay validation as described by the FDA guidelines. The guidelines recommend using the
467 variability in spiked QC samples to estimate assay stability. This gives a good estimation of
468 technical variability. The method to estimate assay stability also takes into account biological
469 variation and thus is more conservative. Moreover, we were able to calculate minimal
470 detectable effects as expected in future measurements using biological samples.

471 To determine assay stability, six samples (from a six-well culture plate), equivalent to 500k
472 cells per well. Fresh samples were measured over four quasi-consecutive days. Each sample
473 was injected three times. Sample concentrations for the analytes were determined with
474 calibration curves. Data for Put were missing for day 1 since they were almost completely
475 suppressed by the addition of cadaverine, as mentioned earlier. By validating the assay in this
476 way, we could capture all variability which allowed us to calculate minimal detectable effects
477 (MDEs) that would be significant in standard null-hypothesis significant tests.

478 Three types of assay variability could be determined, namely inter-day, intra-day and
479 measurement variability. We could distinguish the various types of variation by using a
480 Bayesian multilevel model. This model accounts for hierarchical effects of runs (days) and
481 samples using random effects. This means that it hierarchically models variability across runs
482 and samples, thereby distinguishing the different types of variation. The variation measured
483 between the runs represents the inter-day variability, the variation between samples can be
484 interpreted as the intra-day variability. The remaining variability, *i.e.* variation between the
485 triplicate injections represents measurement variability. Variability is represented as
486 coefficients of variance in percentages (%CV).

487 As for the sources of variation captured by the different measures, inter-day variation considers
488 sources like variation between culture plates (storage time, incubator position) and differences
489 between calibration curves. Inter-day variation could be, for a big part, interpreted as biological
490 variation since signals were corrected by MFC-normalization for signal drift and variation in
491 extraction and biological material. Measurement variability is mostly due to variation in
492 detector response.

493 Inter-day variation was lowest for Put with a median value of around 11%, while Spd and Spm
494 were somewhat higher with median values of 18% and 16% respectively (Fig. 7A, Table 5).
495 As can be seen in Fig. 7A, inter-day estimates showed high variability. This is because only
496 four days were compared, and therefore the uncertainty in the estimates is high. Intra-day
497 variation was highest for Put with a median of 16% while those of Spd and Spm were much
498 lower with median values of 7% and 3.6%. Furthermore, the inter-day estimates were quite
499 accurate for Spd and Spm while the uncertainty in the estimate of Put was higher. The
500 remaining measurement error (variation between triplicates) was also highest for Put with
501 about 9.5%, while those of Spd and Spm were under 4%.

502 By pooling the variances, it was possible to calculate MDEs that would be significant in a null-
503 hypothesis significance test, assuming a two-tailed T-test with $\alpha = 0.05$ (Fig. 7B, Table 5). If
504 assays need to be compared between days the median of the effects, relative to H_0 , that would
505 be picked up as significant were 44% for Put, 39% for Spd and 32% for Spm. For example, if
506 the mean value in a control group for Spm was 100, the effect being picked up as significant
507 ($P < 0.05$) would be smaller than 68 or bigger than 132. Sensitivity within runs was much higher,
508 with MDEs for Put of 37%, 16% for Spd and 9.6% for Spm, relative to H_0 . Taking in account
509 these differences in MDEs between and within runs, it is advisable to design experiments so
510 that relevant comparisons are made between groups with the same run.

511 Method applications

512 After evaluating the method, it was used in two separate use cases. First the effect of
513 SAM486A, a well-known inhibitor of the enzyme S-adenosylmethionine decarboxylase
514 (SAMDC) [12], on PA synthesis in DU145 cells was determined. The second use case was to
515 measure intracellular PA levels of DU145 cells incubated in different culture media conditions.

516 As expected, SAM486A inhibited the synthesis of Spd and Spm completely as can be inferred
517 from the nearly total absence of $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -Spd, $^{13}\text{C}_3$ -Spm and $^{13}\text{C}_6$ -Spm ([M+3], [M+6]) in cells
518 incubated with the inhibitor (Fig. 8). There was also a 2-fold drop in unlabelled Spd and Spm
519 species ([M+0]) which in part can be explained by the fact that the culture medium also
520 contained non-labelled methionine. Moreover, PA pools are not static since PA species are
521 converted to their acetylated forms, can be oxidized and can be excreted from the cell.
522 Therefore, inhibition in synthesis makes that the pools do not get replenished and thus diminish
523 via downstream metabolic processes. On the other hand, Put levels were increased by inhibition
524 of SAMDC. This also makes sense since the SAMDC product, decarboxylated S-
525 adenosylmethionine (dcSAM) is used to convert Put to Spd. Since the production of dcSAMe
526 is strongly inhibited, Put is not converted to upstream PAs and thus accumulates, raising its
527 concentration by about 4-fold.

528 Next the influence of different culture media types on intracellular PA concentrations was
529 explored. We found that PA concentrations indeed varied widely between culture media and
530 show opposite effects between media and analytes (Fig. 9). When compared to complete
531 DMEM, Put and Spm were elevated in DMEM supplemented with dialyzed serum while they
532 were on the same level in HPLM. However, Spm was decreased in dialyzed DMEM while
533 higher in HPLM medium. Assuming no PA presence in media (as it is not an ingredient) Put
534 and Spm synthesis are increased in dialyzed DMEM while Spm synthesis is downregulated.

535 On the other hand, Spm synthesis is upregulated in HPLM. The biological mechanisms driving
536 these differences are beyond the scope of this study and were not further investigated. However,
537 this finding highlights the relevance of controlling the conditions to analyze the levels of PAs
538 in response to a determined stimulus or the status of the cells in a determined pathology.

539

540 Conclusion

541 The method described for the analysis of Put, Spm and Spd showed good performance with
542 respect to chromatography and quantification. Moreover, the sample preparation is
543 straightforward and run time is short, making the method ideal for routine use with substantial
544 sample throughput. Furthermore, with the spiked QC comparisons it was possible to estimate
545 signal attenuation due to matrix effects. This allowed us to use a calibration curve in solution,
546 thereby lowering the LLOQ and subsequently correct for the signal suppression of the various
547 analytes. The MDEs calculated based on assay variability are a guideline for the user to adapt
548 the method for testing their own hypotheses. Moreover, preliminary tests (not shown)
549 suggested that this method was also suitable for measuring acetylated polyamines, however
550 some additional tests need to be performed to ensure this. Similarly, the method could likely
551 be applied to other biological matrices, but this also needs additional optimization steps.

552

553 Supplementary information

554 Code and pretreated signal data for chromatograms and validation experiments is available in

555 the following repository: https://github.com/smvanliempd/polyamine_analysis.

556

557

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559

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575

576 Figure captions

577 *Figure 1)* Mobile phase optimization using 10 μM analyte mix and Grad1. The signals were
578 smoothed by averaging over each two adjacent values. Subsequently smoothed values were
579 scaled on the maximum value per analyte. Mobile phases and gradient are described in Table
580 1 and 2.

581 *Figure 2)* Gradient optimizations using 10 μM analyte mix and MP4. The signals (black lines)
582 were smoothed by averaging over each two adjacent values. Subsequently smoothed values
583 were scaled on the maximum value per analyte and condition. A gaussian was fitted on the data
584 (red lines). Mobile phase and gradients are described in Table 1 and 2.

585 *Figure 3)* Carry over in blank samples, which were directly injected after 10 μM mix, given
586 different concentrations of formic acid in the injection liquid (blue: 0%FA, orange: 0.1% FA,
587 yellow: 0.5% FA). Also shown (black) is a 31 nM mix sample for comparison. The signals were
588 smoothed by averaging over each two adjacent values.

589 *Figure 4)* Extraction efficiency for tested extraction methods (A) and recoveries (B). For
590 visualizations of extraction efficiencies, signals were scaled on the overall data-mean per
591 metabolite (e.g. mean = 1). Values higher than 1 indicate higher signals than the mean for that
592 extraction and *vice versa*, indicating extraction efficiency. For example, for spermine BP (~1.3)
593 performs better than M80 or M50 (~0.8). Analyte recovery from cell homogenates for two
594 spike levels. Recoveries for 1 μM spikes were 90% or higher. Recoveries for spikes at 100 nM
595 could not be determined accurately due to the high background signals in the homogenates.
596 For both extraction and recovery plots, posterior median values within 50% and 80% quantile
597 intervals from Bayesian models (Supp1) were used. M80: 80% MeOH/20% water, M50: 50%
598 MeOH/water, BP: biphasic: (50% MeOH/water):(chloroform).

599 *Figure 5*) Calibration curves for the measured analytes for a single run (A) and deviations from
600 nominal concentrations for all runs (B). Curves were plotted on a log-log scale for better
601 visualization of signals over the total concentration range. Curves were fitted with log-
602 transformed linear regression. For each analyte two curves were fitted for the lower (blue) and
603 the upper part (orange). The common point for both parts was 0.5 μM (vertical dotted line).
604 The horizontal dotted line represents the LLOQ. Adjusted R^2 values for both lower and upper
605 curves are shown. Deviations from nominal concentrations were based on 5 calibration
606 runs. Deviations are given as percentages within the standard of the mean (SEM).

607 *Figure 6*) Measured concentrations in cell cultures over four separate days. Technical, inter-
608 and intra-day variation can be inferred from these data. Each “triplet” of points per day and
609 analyte represents triplicate sample measurements. Six cell samples, extracted from six-well
610 culture plates, per day were measured for four non-consecutive days. The dotted lines represent
611 the grand mean overall measurements per analyte.

612 *Figure 7*) Inter-day, intra-day and measurement variability (A) and minimal significant effects
613 (B) for the assay based on the measured concentrations over four days. Minimal effects were
614 based on pooled standard deviations of inter-, intra-day and measurement (between run) or
615 intra-day and measurement (within run). These pooled standard deviations were then used to
616 calculate a minimal effect that would be significant in a conventional null-hypothesis (H_0)
617 significance test given $\alpha = 0.05$ and $n = 6$ per group.

618 *Figure 8*) Inhibition of PA synthesis by SAM486A using $^{13}\text{C}_5$ labelled methionine as a
619 precursor. Indicated are the stable labelled PA species for Spd and Spm. [M+3] and [M+6]
620 represent species with either 3 or 6 ^{13}C atoms incorporated [M+0] represent the unlabelled
621 species. $\Sigma(\text{all})$ is the sum of the concentrations of the labelled and unlabelled species per sample

622 per analyte. Indicated are the group estimates (median in 50/80 quantile intervals, black dots
623 and lines) and individual sample concentrations (red dots).

624 *Figure 9)* Comparison of cell concentrations of putrescine, spermidine and spermine when
625 using different culture media. Indicated are the group estimates (median in 50/80 quantile
626 intervals, black dots and lines) and individual sample concentrations (red dots).

627

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666

667

668 Tables

669

670 Table 1) Mobile phase optimization. Formic acid (FA) and ammonium formate (AmFo)

671 content in both aqueous and organic mobile phases. Same elution gradient^a was used for all

672 tests.

Mobile phase ^b	FA (% v)	AmFo (mM)
MP1	0.1	0
MP2	0.1	1
MP3	0.1	2.5
MP4	0.25	2.5
MP5	0.5	5

673

674 a) Gradient was Grad1 as shown in Table 2)

675 b) Aqueous phase (A) always consisted of water and organic phase (B) consisted of water in 90% (v/v/v)

676 ACN.

677

678 Table 2) LC optimization. Gradients tested.

Gradient	%A start gradient	Time gradient (min)	%A end gradient	Time strong (min)	%A end strong	Time gradient (min)	%A Start equilibration	Equilibration time (min)
Grad1	50	2	100	2.4	100	0.1	50	1
Grad2	40	2	100	2.4	100	0.1	40	1
Grad3	50	3	100	1.4	100	0.1	50	1
Grad4	40	3	100	1.4	100	0.1	40	1
Grad5	45	3	100	1.4	100	0.1	45	1
Grad6	50	3.5	100	0.9	100	0.1	50	1
Grad7	52	3.5	100	0.9	100	0.1	52	1

679

680 Table 3) Chromatographic resolutions^a for tested mobile phases and gradients.

Optimalization	Gradient	Mobile phase	R1	R2
Mobile phase	Grad1	MP1	2.7	2.3
Mobile phase	Grad1	MP2	3.7	4.4
Mobile phase	Grad1	MP3	7.9	9.3
Mobile phase	Grad1	MP4	6.6	9.3
Mobile phase	Grad1	MP5	9.7	12.1
Gradient	Grad1	MP4	7.2	8.8
Gradient	Grad2	MP4	11.9	10.0
Gradient	Grad3	MP4	7.5	10.9
Gradient	Grad4	MP4	13.8	11.9
Gradient	Grad5	MP4	10.4	12.3
Gradient	Grad6	MP4	8.7	12.1
Gradient	Grad7	MP4	11.7	12.5

681

682 a) R1: resolution between putrescine and spermidine; R2: resolution between spermidine and spermine.

683

684 Table 4) Assay metrics including recovery, signal attenuation. Values are given as the
685 posterior median with the 50% quantile interval between parentheses.

686

Analyte	Recovery (%) ^a		Attenuation ^b
	100 nM	1 μ M	
Putrescine	76 (60-88)	97 (95-99)	0.35 (0.32-0.38)
Spermidine	82 (68-92)	92 (88-96)	0.59 (0.55-0.68)
Spermine	78 (58-91)	89 (85-94)	0.87 (0.83-0.91)

687

688 a) Recovery for two spike levels, *i.e.* 100 nM and 100 μ M.

689 b) Attenuation was defined as the factor by which the signal in the biological matrix was attenuated with
690 respect to the signal in solution.

691

692 Table 5) Assay metrics including variation and minimal effects. Values are given as the
693 posterior median with the 50% quantile interval between parentheses.

694

Analyte	Sources of variation (%CV) ^a			Minimal effects ^b (% H ₀)	
	inter-day	intra-day	measurement	Between days	Within days
Putrescine	11	16	9.5	29	24
	(6.4-16)	(14-18)	(8.7-10)	(26-34)	(22-27)
Spermidine	18	7.0	3.9	26	10
	(14-24)	(6.2-7.9)	(3.6-4.2)	(21-33)	(9.5-11)
Spermine	16	3.6	3.2	21	6.3
	(12-20)	(3.2-4.2)	(3-3.5)	(17-27)	(5.9-6.8)

695

696 a) %CV: coefficient of variation: 100*sd/mean.

697 b) Based on pooled standard deviations. Assuming a two-tailed T-test with $\alpha = 0.05$ and $n = 6$ per group.

698

699

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

A**Fig. 4**

A

B

Fig. 5

A

B

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9